

MODELLING THE COMBINED EFFECTS OF IONISING RADIATION AND CHEMICAL POLLUTANTS ON WILDLIFE POPULATIONS*

J. Vives i Batlle¹ (✉)

¹Belgian Nuclear Research Centre (SCK•CEN), Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium. Tel: +32 (0)14 33 88 05, Fax: +32 (0)14 32 10 56, e-mail: jordi.vives.i.batlle@sckcen.be

This is a preprint of an article in the Journal of Environmental Radioactivity (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2025.107615>)

*This paper is dedicated to the memory of Professor Nick Beresford

Abstract

A population model is presented to study the combined effects of ionising radiation and chemical pollutants on wildlife. The model is based on first order, non-linear and logistic differential equations combining mortality, morbidity and reproduction phenomena with life history data and ecological interactions. Acclimation is considered as a possible mechanism to study theoretically this effect at low levels of radiation or chemical concentration. Radiation and chemical-induced damages are represented by a ‘repairing pool’ mediating between healthy, damaged, acclimated, and irrecoverable individuals. Damages to population, fecundity and the repairing pool are represented by a linear-quadratic function combining radiation dose and chemical concentration terms. The endpoints of the model are repairable damages (morbidity), impairment of reproductive ability and mortality.

The model is evaluated with a mixed ionising radiation/arsenate demonstration scenario to illustrate the combined effect of radiation and chemical pollutants upon the sustainability of a hypothetical vole population, including the influence of acclimation, given the assumption that the repair of both radiation and toxicity damages share the same mechanism. A sensitivity analysis of the model illustrates the effects of combining radiation dose and chemical concentration on self-repairing and reproductive ability for the population, exploring cases of antagonism and synergism by varying the relevant model parameters.

This model provides a conceptual framework to address mixed radiological and chemical effects to wildlife populations. It can be used to assess the robustness of the benchmarks used in wildlife radiological assessment, informing ongoing regulatory debates on their applicability to mixed stressor situations. Future research will enable to draw conclusions about the most restrictive mixed exposure situations in terms of effects to the population.

Keywords: Ecological risk assessment; Non-human biota; Multiple stressors; Population model

1. Introduction

Modelling approaches have been developed to understand the effects of ionising radiation at the population level. These models are not yet used routinely in regulatory environmental risk assessments, but a growing number is becoming available to guide modellers and risk assessors to address different ecological risk assessment questions (Accolla et al., 2020; Raimondo et al., 2021). Within radioecology, the goal is to understand the factors influencing wildlife population responses to radiation, informing discussions on the ecological relevance of current environmental protection criteria (Vives i Batlle et al., 2022; Vives i Batlle et al., 2020). The need for consistency of approach between chemical and radiological impact assessment is a part of these ongoing discussions because there are numerous radiological exposure scenarios for non-human biota where radionuclide pollution coexists with chemical pollution.

Nuclear power plant liquid discharges contain an array of chemicals, as do nuclear waste disposal, spent nuclear fuel reprocessing, uranium mining and milling and land disposals from the phosphate industries (Müller et al., 2000; Tayibi et al., 2009; Vandenhove et al., 2015) (Fig. 1). Estimating how the effects of these pollutants combine with radiation is an important goal for radioecology (Pirota et al., 2022).

Figure 1: Examples of chemical contaminants present along radionuclides in different exposure situations – based on information from Vandenhove et al. (2011)

Regulators need a practical approach for environmental impact studies able to compare toxicity and radiotoxicity at the population level for wildlife, without recourse to complex biological modelling at the molecular level. This is because, in addition to following guidelines and recommendations, they benefit from looking at the additional body of scientific work and welcome additional demonstration of robustness or modelling at the ecological level, to boost confidence in decision making. Population modelling can be used to this effect, helping to verify that current benchmarks for the protection of wildlife are valid at the ecosystem level, in order to evaluate the robustness of the radiation protection system for biota (Beresford and Vives i Batlle, 2021). This paper formulates a dynamic population effects model, where radiation and chemicals interact in the presence of ecological interactions.

2. State-of-the-art on population modelling for mixed contaminants

2.1. General approaches for population modelling

The most directly relevant source for population effects modelling in radioecology (Alonzo et al., 2012) covers two basic approaches: (a) physiology-based matrix population models (Lance et al., 2012), including Leslie matrices (Caswell, 2001), and (b) ordinary differential equation (ODE) dynamic models (Kryshev and Sazykina, 2015; Kryshev et al., 2006; Kryshev et al., 2008; Vives i Batlle, 2012; Vives i Batlle et al., 2009). Matrix models have been used to compare radiosensitivity between individual and population endpoints (Alonzo et al., 2016), whilst ODE models have been used to simulate the range of radiation effects in combination with ecological interactions (Vives i Batlle, 2012).

A review by Galic et al. (2010) reveals a number of structured population models that take account of different age classes of species, but do not take into account the effects of mixtures of contaminants. An additional source (Vandenhove et al., 2011) reviews models for mixed contaminant exposure, effect and risk assessment in ecotoxicology and evaluation of their usefulness for radioecology. Our study began with an update of this review, to bring the most up-to-date information for various categories of models.

2.1.1. Basic risk assessment approaches

Risk assessment modelling of chemical mixtures is based on two concepts: concentration addition (CA), which applies to substances with the same mode of action so they do not affect the biological activity of each other (Loewe and Muischnek, 1926), and independent action (IA), in which the components have a different mode of action, acting on different physiological systems (Escher et al., 2020).

For CA, in the case of n contaminants with different individual y_i -percent effective concentrations (EC_{y_i} s) present in fractions $p_i = \frac{c_i}{c_{tot}}$, it can be shown that they act together with an “effective” $EC_y(\text{mixture}) = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{p_i}{EC_{y_i}}}$ where $p_i = \frac{c_i}{c_{tot}}$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1$ (Altenburger et al., 2000). CA is the default conservative approach for multi-substance risk assessment. For IA, the overall effect is calculated as $\varepsilon_{mix} = \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - \varepsilon_{C_i})$ (Backhaus et al., 2000).

If data are available for the endpoints of interest, CA or IA mixture effects can be predicted and statistical analysis can then reveal if observed effects are higher (synergism) or lower (antagonism) than expected. Such data often comes as dose response curves (DRCs), which describe the magnitude of the response E as a function of exposure to the stressor(s) after a certain exposure time D . These curves are typically monotonic and sigmoidal-shape and can be fit to a logistic function, such as the Hill equation or the Logit curve.

A comparison of CA and IA for mixtures of compounds has been performed (Cedergreen et al., 2008), and studies have been carried-out to investigate observed deviations from these models (de Zwart and Posthuma, 2009; Jonker et al., 2005). An approach for ecological risk assessment of mixtures of radiological and chemical stressors already exists (Beaumelle et al., 2017; Garnier-Laplace et al., 2009). This approach applies species sensitivity distributions of ionising radiation and chemicals in combination with both CA and IA, in order to calculate a Multi-Substance Potentially Affected Fractions of species (msPAF), representing the combined ecological impact of radiation and chemical substances.

2.1.2. Toxicokinetic-Toxicodynamic (TK-TD) Models

Toxicokinetic-Toxicodynamic (TK-TD) Models integrate the processes toxicokinetics (TK), dealing with uptake and turnover of substances into the body of an organism, and toxicodynamics (TD), dealing with the effects of the toxicant on the organism. TK modelling is carried out with relatively simple compartment linear models involving physiological parameters such as uptake rates and biological half-lives (Whicker and Schultz, 1982). TD modelling has been typically dealt with various approaches such as DebTox or individual-based models, as described below.

By integrating CA and IA theory into TK-TD modelling principles, it is possible to calculate the combined toxicity of different metals (Ashauer et al., 2007; Cedergreen et al., 2017). The approach has been used to predict mixture toxicity of metals in *Daphnia magna* (Tan and Wang, 2012), pesticides on aquatic invertebrates (Focks et al., 2014), and metals on fish (Yang et al., 2021). Interactions between organic chemicals (Mackay et al., 2014) and between metals and natural stressors (e.g. salinity) have also been investigated (Chen et al., 2017).

Over the past decades, biotic ligand models (BLM) have been proposed to study metal bioaccumulation in aquatic organisms (Wang and Tan, 2019). The BLM is a chemical equilibrium model assuming that toxicity is determined by the strength of metal binding to the site of toxicity in organisms. BLMs can be applied to mixture toxicity (Borgmann et al., 2008), with work available on metal toxicity mixtures in aquatic biota (Gao et al., 2016; Heijerick et al., 2009) and effect of copper and zinc in *Daphnia magna* (De Schamphelaere et al., 2002; Heijerick et al., 2009; Vlaeminck et al., 2021).

2.1.3. DebTox models

DebTox models incorporate the dynamic energy budget (DEB) idea of mathematically following the energy budget of an individual organism throughout its life cycle (Kooijman, 1986; Kooijman, 2000; Nisbet et al., 2000), using this to simulate how chemicals are absorbed, cycled within organisms (toxicokinetics) and how these processes influence an organism's health and life history (toxicodynamics) (Alonzo et al., 2015; Alonzo et al., 2014). An extensive curated data collection exists to parameterise these models with life history data (AMP, 2020).

DEB modelling to ecotoxicology involves linking toxicant concentrations to the effects on life history traits over time in a TD-TK modelling approach (Alonzo et al., 2014; Baas et al., 2010b; Baas et al., 2010a). DEB models of individual organisms have been used to analyze data from ecotoxicological tests of chemical compounds (Jager and Zimmer, 2012; Kooijman and Bedaux, 1996), and as a basis for modelling the dynamics of structured populations (Metz and Diekmann, 1986). Some applications include the effects of binary mixtures of Cu and Cd on *Daphnia magna* (Matyja, 2023) and studies of depleted uranium toxicity (Alonzo et al., 2014; Massarin et al., 2011), helping to interpret experimental data (Massarin et al., 2010; Plaire et al., 2013).

Applying the approach to ionizing radiation implies defining a metric for radiological stress (Alonzo et al., 2015; Alonzo et al., 2014). A DEBTox model for chronic gamma radiation effects in the nematode *C. elegans* was recently published (Lecomte-Pradines et al., 2017), where as other studies (Augustine et al., 2012; Goussen et al., 2015; Massarin et al., 2011) have dealt with exposure to depleted uranium.

2.1.4. Individual-Based Models (IBM)

In IBM models, individuals are modelled and population effects are obtained as emergent properties (Mebane et al., 2020; Mintram et al., 2020; Nys et al., 2020). Each organism can have its own life history, incorporated as state variables (Railsback and Grimm, 2019). IBMs can also incorporate DEB theory in their equations, as shown by Koch and De Schampelaere (2000).

An IBM framework was used to study the effects of copper and zinc on *Daphnia magna* populations in the aforementioned study by Vlaeminck et al. (2021). Other examples of DEB modelling studies addressing the toxicity of organic chemical mixtures (Vlaeminck et al., 2022) for organics and mixtures of metals, also in *Daphnia magna* (Hansul et al., 2021), and in nematodes (Jager et al., 2014; Margerit et al., 2016), to give a few examples.

2.1.5. Population dynamics ODE modelling

Population Dynamics Models are either Leslie matrices implementing stage-structured models or compartmental models, based on solving a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) by dividing the population into different subgroups or compartments, each representing a specific life stage or condition such as age, sex, health status (Vives i Batlle et al., 2020). Toxicity can be incorporated into an ODE population dynamics model by factorising the repair mechanism in biota populations (Kryshev et al., 2006; Kryshev et al., 2008; Sazykina and Kryshev, 2016; Sazykina and Kryshev, 2012).

A line of models has been developed adopting this principle, to study the effects of radiation on wildlife populations under a variety of ecological situations (Vives i Batlle, 2012; Vives i Batlle et al., 2022; Vives i Batlle et al., 2012; Vives i Batlle et al., 2020). A pioneering mathematical treatment of dose-effect relationships for fish exposed to chronic ionising radiation (Kryshev et al., 2008) addressed the combined ecological action of radiation and parasite infestation, signalling the direction for the mathematical approach adopted here.

2.2. Available experimental studies

Studies exist on the effects in the Atlantic salmon following mixed exposure to heavy metals and radiation (Heier et al., 2013; Mothersill et al., 2014; Salbu et al., 2008). A study of joint toxicity of cadmium and ionizing radiation on zooplankton and green microalgae is also available (Bradshaw et al., 2019; Nascimento et al., 2016). There are also investigations on the combined effect of uranium and gamma radiation in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Vanhoudt et al., 2010), as well studies combining γ -radiation and organic chemical in plankton (Nascimento et al., 2015), to name a few examples.

By far, the aquatic plant *Lemna minor* seems to have received the most attention, with studies involving gamma radiation and copper (Bodnar and Cheban, 2022), zinc (Bodnar and Cheban, 2023), uranium and organic compounds (Gonzales et al., 2023). A recent study (Van Dyck, 2023) explored the uptake and effects of stable Co and Cs together with γ -radiation.

The data available (mainly from the evidence of chemicals) reveal that contaminant mixtures often give additive effects, but not always, as effects induced by mixtures of contaminants can deviate from the sum of individual effects and compound mixtures can exert effects at concentrations in which the single contaminants do not.

2.3. Conclusions on state-of-the-art

Overall, although several representative mixture toxicity modelling studies exist for chemicals (with *Daphnia magna* and *Lemna minor* being particularly well covered), but studies involving radionuclides in the mixture are more scarce, except for the special case of uranium, which can be treated as a toxic chemical (Margerit et al., 2015). This highlights a knowledge gap, given the exposure situations involving radionuclides combined with other stressors (Salbu et al., 2019). The assessment of how chemical and radiation stresses interact is an emerging field, calling for advances in modelling to quantify and assess these effects to build regulatory confidence that there are no unexpected impacts on populations.

The above approaches offer various options for dynamic modelling. Most are complex and computationally demanding, but ODE modelling offers a more simplified route to conceptualise the dynamic interplay of radiation and chemical toxicity in biota, treating the damage and repair processes at the phenomenological level of modelling rather than at the fully process-based molecular level, and integrating toxicity in context of population dynamics. This practical approach is more suitable for guiding regulators, who have so far not routinely used these models because of their perceived (rather than actual) complexity and inherent uncertainties.

The ODE approach is particularly suitable to address, in a practical way and with the minimum of complexity, the regulatory question of how robust and defensible the existing radiation protection benchmarks are for biota populations in mixed exposure conditions, being flexible enough to be used as a stable base to add new features (ecological, ecotoxicological and radioecological factors), bridging the gap between science and regulation.

The approach is intended to help formulate scenarios with different exposure rates and basic population parameters to underpin discussions with stakeholders on what kinds of scenarios and species are more sensitive. It addresses the need for detailed considerations on populations in mixed exposure scenarios, without aiming to change the current protection system.

3. Development of a dynamic mixed stressors effects model

Our ODE model is grounded on the principles established in the pioneering radioecology projects STAR (Alonzo et al., 2015) and MODARIA (Beresford and Vives i Batlle, 2021), using a compact system of first-order differential equations, as shown in the sections below.

3.1. Description of the mathematical approach

The starting point (Figure 2) is a logistic population model for radiation (Vives i Batlle, 2012) which was validated against effects data from the FREDERICA database (Coplestone et al., 2008; FREDERICA, 2006). This type of model has been successfully modified and adapted to various ecological situations (Vives i Batlle et al., 2022; Vives i Batlle et al., 2012).

Figure 2: Dual-age class logistic population model, adapted from Vives i Batlle (2012)

In this study, for simplicity, a set of logistic ODEs is employed, describing a single age-class population inhabiting a homogeneous spatial domain. The carrying capacity of the population is constant and migration is not considered. The model considers two interacting stressors (radiation and chemical), although this can be easily modified to consider multicomponent chemical mixtures.

The radiation dose or the chemical concentration received by the biota, which are input parameters for the model, detract from the organism's ability to self-repair and its fecundity. In future work, a biokinetic (dynamic) module will be included, factorising the intake rate, the absorption efficiency and the biological half-life of elimination as additional parameters (Vives i Batlle et al., 2008), resulting in a full toxicokinetic – toxicodynamic model.

The model includes acclimation acting at low levels of radiation dose or chemical concentration. Acclimation is defined here as a temporary de-sensitisation within a single organism that improves its survival, in response to low doses of (radio)pollutants, constrained by the genome of the individual. It differs from biological adaptation, in that there is no acquisition or recombination of genes leading to better survival over multiple generations.

3.1.1. Governing equations

Figure 3 shows the system of 5 linear first order differential equations, substantially developed from an earlier model version (Beresford and Vives i Batlle, 2021; Vives i Batlle et al., 2022). They describe a system of healthy (X), sick (Y) and acclimated (W) members of a population, whose reproduction is controlled by a fecundity pool (F) and its ability to repair damages is controlled by a repairing pool (R).

$$\text{Healthy organisms: } \frac{dX}{dt} = rF \frac{X}{T} \left(1 - \frac{T}{K}\right) - dX + p\kappa YR + \eta W - (\alpha D + \beta C + \gamma CD)X$$

$$\text{Sick organisms: } \frac{dY}{dt} = rF \frac{Y}{T} \left(1 - \frac{T}{K}\right) - dY - \epsilon Y - \kappa YR + (\alpha D + \beta C + \gamma CD)X$$

$$\text{Acclimated organisms: } \frac{dW}{dt} = rF \frac{W}{T} \left(1 - \frac{T}{K}\right) - dW + (1-p)\kappa YR - \eta W$$

$$\text{Fecundity: } \frac{dF}{dt} = \mu_f F \left(1 - \frac{F}{K}\right) - rF \left(1 - \frac{T}{K}\right) - (\alpha_f D + \beta_f C + \gamma_f CD)F$$

$$\text{Acclimated fecundity: } \frac{dF_A}{dt} = \mu_f F_A \left(1 - \frac{F_A}{K}\right) - rF_A \left(1 - \frac{T}{K}\right)$$

Recovery pool:
$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \mu_r R \left(1 - \frac{R}{K}\right) - \kappa_r YR - (\alpha_r D + \beta_r C + \gamma_r CD)R$$

Equation terms: **Logistic terms**, **Repair**, **Mixture toxicity**, **Acclimation**, **Natural death**, **Radiation lethality**

Figure 3: Equations of the ODR model for radiation and chemicals, with colour-coded explanation of the different processes

The above equations contain the principal input parameters: the concentration of chemical in the environment (C , in mg kg^{-1}) and the dose rate given to the organism (D , in milligrays per day). The radiation dose and chemical concentration are contained in the linear-quadratic “effects equation”: $\phi = \alpha D + \beta C + \gamma DC$. This effects equation can easily be generalised to non-binary mixtures of N different contaminants, adopting the form $\phi = \alpha D + \sum_{i=1}^N \beta_i C_i + D \sum_{i=1}^N \gamma_i C_i + \sum_{i \neq j=1}^N \gamma_{ij} C_i C_j$.

In the case of no radiation or chemical stressor, whence all derivatives equal zero, there are no sick or acclimated individuals and therefore $X = F = T$, and so $rX \left(1 - \frac{X}{K}\right) = dX$ with the non-trivial solution $X = K \left(1 - \frac{d}{r}\right)$. This means that the model stabilises to a value of $X < K$ after a warm-up period of about 200 days. The warm-up period should be understood as a mathematical pre-adjustment time for the model to move from initial conditions to a state in which the population is in balance, not considering the effects of pollutants and radiation.

Non-acclimated and acclimated populations have a different fecundity pool, instead of a shared one. This improves the representation, as members of the population in acclimated state are more correctly assumed to be temporarily protected from the effects of a radioactive or chemical pollutant. Both fecundities have the same initial value, equal to the number of individuals a time = 0.

The effects equation makes this model quite general, since it covers concentration Addition CA (same mode of action) with possibility for synergism (enhanced effects) or antagonism (reduced effects), depending on the sign of γ . The model is also quite general in the sense of being able to calculate effects at low concentrations based on acute data, owing to the dose-dependent recovery pool. Recent studies on transforming acute ecotoxicity data into chronic data will allow us in future to verify and improve upon this method (Beaugelin-Seiller et al., 2020).

3.1.2. Considerations on units

The radiation dose by an internally incorporated radionuclide D can be expressed in “concentration units”, given that $D(\text{Gy } d^{-1}) = \frac{A_{org}(\text{Bq})}{M_{org}(\text{kg})} \times D_C(\text{Gy } \text{kg } d^{-1} \text{Bq}^{-1})$ where A_{org} , M_{org} and D_C are the activity, mass and radionuclide-dependent dose coefficient for the organism, with $D_C(\text{Gy } \text{kg } d^{-1} \text{Bq}^{-1}) = 2.4 \times 10^{-5} \times D_C(\mu\text{Gy } \text{kg } h^{-1} \text{Bq}^{-1})$. The activity of radionuclide in the organism is linked to the mass of radionuclide in it via the radionuclide specific activity SpA_{rad} as $A_{org}(\text{Bq}) = 10^{-6} \times M_{org}^{rad}(\text{mg}) \times SpA_{rad}(\text{Bq } \text{kg}^{-1})$. Thus:

$$D(\text{mGy } d^{-1}) = 2.4 \times 10^{-11} \times C_{org}^{rad}(\text{mg } \text{kg}^{-1}) \times SpA_{rad}(\text{Bq } \text{kg}^{-1}) \times D_C(\mu\text{Gy } \text{kg } h^{-1} \text{Bq}^{-1})$$

It therefore follows that $\alpha D + \beta C_{org}^{chem} + \gamma C_{org}^{chem} D = (2.4 \times 10^{-11} SpA_{rad} D_C \alpha) C_{org}^{rad} + \beta C_{org}^{chem} + (2.4 \times 10^{-11} SpA_{rad} D_C \gamma) C_{org}^{rad} C_{org}^{chem} \equiv \hat{\alpha} C_{org}^{rad} + \beta C_{org}^{chem} + \hat{\gamma} C_{org}^{rad} C_{org}^{chem}$ where C_{org}^{rad} and C_{org}^{chem} are the mass concentrations in mg kg^{-1} of the radionuclide and the chemical in

the organism, respectively. It therefore follows that $\hat{\alpha} = (2.4 \times 10^{-11} SpA_{rad} D_C) \alpha$, $\hat{\gamma} = (2.4 \times 10^{-11} SpA_{rad} D_C) \gamma$, where D_C is in $\mu\text{Gy kg h}^{-1} \text{Bq}^{-1}$, and SpA_{rad} is in Bq kg^{-1} .

3.1.3. Model set-up

The model was set up in Cherwell Scientific's software ModelMaker 4 (Citra, 1997), with equations solved by the Runge-Kutta method with an accuracy of 10^{-5} and a minimum value of 10^{-11} . It features a switch to eliminate the acclimation process, given that this part of the model, based on Wodarz et al. (2014) is more conjectural, being developed for single-cell populations.

A picture of the model as displayed by the ModelMaker 4 software is given in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Model schematic including healthy, sick, and acclimated organisms in the presence of chemical and radioactive stressors

3.2. Model parameterisation

Our hypothetical scenario involves a population of voles (*Microtus agrestis*), combining a γ -radiation dose rate with a concentration of sodium arsenate in the soil. This scenario uses realistic environmental data, but it is designed for demonstration purposes, without constituting an assessment for a specific situation. A LD_{50} of 6.2 Gy can be adopted for mouse (Sazykina and Kryshev, 2016), which is consistent with acute lethal doses ($LD_{50/30}$) of typically 6-10 Gy for small mammals (ICRP, 2009). Unlike the LD_{50} for radiation, the LD_{50} for the chemical depends on the element used. The LD_{50} for Na_3AsO_4 in rat and mouse is 112 mg kg^{-1} (or 40 mg kg^{-1} for As) (Hartwig, 2016).

3.2.1. Determination of the LD_{50} , the lethality rate ϵ and the parameters α , β and γ

A summary of the model parameters is given in Table 1. Some parameters can be obtained by a deduction process (Kryshev and Ryabov, 2000; Kryshev and Sazykina, 2015; Kryshev et al., 2006; Kryshev et al., 2008; Sazykina and Kryshev, 2016; Sazykina and Kryshev, 2012), as explained previously (Vives i Batlle et al., 2020).

Table 1: Summary of parameters for the radiation case, and analogously derived conjectural parameters for the chemical case.

Parameter - radiation	Parameter - chemical	Description	Value (radiation)	Value (chemical)	Alternative calculation method
<u>Radiation and chemotoxicity parameters</u>					
LD _{50/30} (mGy)	LD _{50/30} (mg kg ⁻¹)	Half-lethal dose rate or concentration	6200	112	
D (mGy d ⁻¹)	C (mg kg ⁻¹)	Dose rate or concentration	Variable depending on case study		
α (mGy ⁻¹)	β (kg mg ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	Initial radiation damages	0.00011	0.00021	$\frac{\ln 2}{LD_{50/30}}$ (radiation), $\frac{\ln 2}{30LD_{50/30}}$ (chemical)
ε (d ⁻¹)		Lethality rate of unreparable individuals	0.023		$\frac{\ln 2}{30}$ (all cases)
α _r (mGy ⁻¹)	β _r (kg mg ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	Damages to the reproductive system	0.0011	0.0021	α _r = 10 × α, β _r = 10 × β
α _r (mGy ⁻¹)	β _r (kg mg ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	Damages to repairing pool	0.0022	0.0041	α _r = 2 × α _f , β _r = 2 × β _f
κ (d ⁻¹)		Sick regeneration rate	0.2		LLT ratio is < 2% so κ ≈ 1/R _{max} . Change to 0.9 for high LET radiation ¹ or very toxic chemicals.
κ _r (d ⁻¹)		Recovery pool depletion rate	0.21		κ _r = 1.5 × κ
μ _r (d ⁻¹)		Recovery pool regeneration rate	0.032		
μ _r (d ⁻¹)		Fecundity pool regeneration rate	0.021		μ _r = 1.5 × μ _f
p ₀ (-)	q ₀ (-)	Coefficients for acclimation probability	0.11	0.11	p ₀ = q ₀ and q ₁ = $\frac{\beta p_1}{\alpha L}$
p ₁ (mGy ⁻¹)	q ₁ (kg mg ⁻¹)		0.023	74.4	
η (d ⁻¹)		Rate of conversion of acclimated back to healthy	0.000395		$\eta = \frac{\ln(2)}{L}$
<u>Life history parameters</u>					
L (d)		Vole lifespan	1753.2		
d (d ⁻¹)		Natural death rate	0.0031		
r (d ⁻¹)		Reproduction rate	0.06		

Assuming no natural death, repair, acclimation, or reproduction (i.e. $\kappa = \eta = p = 0$), the equation for initial damages becomes $\frac{dX}{dt} \approx -(\alpha D + \beta C)X$ giving $X = X_0 e^{-(\alpha D + \beta C)t}$. The time for 50% damages (T_{50}) is calculated as follows: $X_0 e^{-(\alpha D + \beta C)T_{50}} = \frac{1}{2} X_0$, so $T_{50} = \frac{\ln 2}{\alpha D + \beta C}$.

It is an adequate approximation that $\varepsilon = \frac{\ln(2)}{30} = 0.023 \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Vives i Batlle et al., 2009). If $C = 0$, letting $T_{50} = 30 \text{ d}$ would kill 50% of the population if the dose received is equal to the LD_{50/30}. The LD₅₀ is a calibration point used to calculate the parameter α describing radiation damage of the repairing pool, whereupon $30D = LD_{50/30} = \frac{\ln 2}{\alpha}$ and $\alpha = \frac{\ln 2}{LD_{50/30}} = 1.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mGy}^{-1}$. For chemical toxicity, the same approach is followed but the relevant magnitude is now the LD₅₀ (mg kg⁻¹). Hence, a concentration of LC_{50/30} applied to the organism over 30 days would kill 50% of the population. By the same argument as above, $\beta EC_{30/50} \times 30 = \ln 2$

¹ This is because high-LET radiation (such as neutrons and α-rays) are more destructive to biological material than low-LET radiation (such as X- and γ-rays).

and therefore $\beta = \frac{\ln 2}{30LD_{50/30}} = 2.06 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kg mg}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$ (note the difference in units, since the relevant parameter is the concentration rather than the dose rate).

For the term describing mutually interacting effects, analogous reasoning leads to $\gamma = \frac{\ln(2)}{30 \times LDC_{50}}$. The parameter LDC_{50} is unknown and needs to be measured (its value is discussed here by way of sensitivity analysis).

3.2.2. *Fecundity and recovery pool parameters*

The aforesaid parameter deduction process assumes that initial damages appear at lower doses/concentrations than reproduction effects (stem cells for reproduction are more sensitive than those producing lymphocytes and platelets), which in turn appear at lower concentrations than mortality effects. So, the conditions $\alpha \ll \alpha_f < \alpha_r$ and $\beta \ll \beta_f < \beta_r$ can be imposed (Kryshev et al., 2008). One can therefore use $\alpha_f = 10 \times \alpha = 1.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mGy}^{-1}$ and $\alpha_r = 2 \times \alpha_f = 2.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mGy}^{-1}$ and the equivalent for the parameters $\beta_f = 2.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg mg}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$ and $\beta_r = 4.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg mg}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$.

The parameter κ (rate of output for the repairing process) was taken as 0.2 d^{-1} (Sazykina and Kryshev, 2016). As per κ_r (non-lethal damages recovery rate), a value of 0.21 d^{-1} was adopted, consistent with a previous vole modelling study (Vives i Batlle et al., 2020) where it was assumed that $\kappa_r = 1.1\kappa$, given that repairing pool processes are somewhat faster than those occurring at the population level (Kryshev et al., 2008). However, it is possible to use the equation for the reversibly damaged sick population (radiation case only), ignoring reproduction and natural death: $\frac{dY}{dt} \approx \alpha DX - (\epsilon + \kappa R)Y$, which gives a loss due to lethal damages plus repaired damages with a combined rate $\epsilon + \kappa R$. The ratio “lethal damages / total (lethal + repaired) damages” expressed by the ratio $LTD = \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon + \kappa R_{max}}$ is low, no more than 2% for low LET radiation (Kryshev et al., 2008). This gives an approximate value of κ .

The rate constant μ_R controls the speed at which the repairing pool builds itself back up to R_{max} . A value of 0.032 d^{-1} for mouse (*Mus musculus*) from Sazykina (2018) shows that a timescale of this order is plausible at least for males, due to cell division and repopulation of the spermatogonial stem cell pool. Since processes occurring within the repairing pool are somewhat faster than reproductive processes (Kryshev et al., 2008), one can assume $\mu_R \approx 1.5\mu_F$ and, by a symmetry, that the regeneration rate μ_F is 0.021 d^{-1} .

3.2.3. *Alternative parameterisation for high-LET radiation*

High-LET radiation is more destructive to biological material. This requires re-estimation of different parameters κ and κ_R by the LTD ratio method expounded above. Instead of a low LTD value of 2%, one can now assume that LTD is high at 90%, so $\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon + \kappa R_{max}} = 0.9$ and therefore $\kappa \approx \frac{1}{400R_{max}}$ and $\kappa_R \approx 1.5\kappa = \frac{1.5}{400R_{max}}$ are recommended for α -radiation (Vives i Batlle et al., 2009).

3.2.4. *Parameterisation of the acclimation system*

The parameter η in Figure 3 drives the acclimation mechanism as it determines the time the organism remains in a protected state.

Wodarz et al. (2014) give an equation for the probability of forsaking acclimation and instead going into successful full repair as a function of cumulative dose: $p_R = \frac{p_0 + p_1 \int_{T-L}^T DR(t) dt}{1 + p_0 + p_1 \int_{T-L}^T DR(t) dt}$, where p_0 and p_1 are experimentally derived coefficients (Wodarz et al., 2014), and L is a time integration period.

By analogy, for chemicals (where the governing force is concentration), $p_C(c) = \frac{q_0 + q_1 c}{1 + q_0 + q_1 c}$. Therefore, the combined probability for acclimation either by radiation or a hazardous chemical (which are not mutually exclusive events) is $p = p_R(DR) + p_C(c) - p_R(DR) \times p_C(c)$.

Values of p_0 and p_1 for cell lines from Wodarz et al. (2014) are 1.1×10^{-1} and $2.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mGy}^{-1}$, respectively. It is assumed here that the chemical concentration follows the same mechanism. In the equation for p_R , the coefficient p_0 is non-dimensional and p_1 has units of mGy^{-1} . To scale-up p_1 to the mass of a small rodent of $3.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}$ from the mass of a human blood cell, which is about $2.7 \times 10^{-14} \text{ kg}$ (Phillips et al., 2012), the plausibility argument can be used that the adaptive mechanism scales allometrically to the power of 0.25. The average mass of a human blood cell is about $2.7 \times 10^{-14} \text{ kg}$ (Phillips et al., 2012). The animal mass used in our model is $3.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}$; therefore, a scaling factor of $\left(\frac{3.5 \times 10^{-2}}{2.7 \times 10^{-14}}\right)^{0.25} = 10^3$ is proposed, giving a value (which can only be conjectural at this stage) of $p_1 = 2.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mGy}^{-1}$. The main implication here is that p_1 has a low value compared with p_0 and, therefore, that the probability of acclimation tends to a relatively dose-independent value $\frac{1}{1+p_0}$ for low cumulative doses.

The equation for p_C implies that q_0 is also non-dimensional whereas q_1 must have units of kg mg^{-1} . Using the units equivalence $\alpha D \equiv \beta C$ in the effects equation $\alpha D + \beta C + \gamma DC$, and given our hypothesis that the repair mechanism for radiation and for the chemical pollutant are the same, by dimensional considerations, $p_0 = q_0 = 1.1 \times 10^{-1}$ and $q_1 = \left(\frac{\alpha L}{\beta}\right) p_1 = 7.4 \times 10^1$, where L is the time integration parameter of the equation for p_R .

Wodarz et al. (2014) give $\eta = 0.15 \text{ min}^{-1}$ for individual cell lines. For complex multicellular organisms, which have a longer reproduction cycle (several years) than individual cell lines, this parameter must necessarily be lower. Based on the intuitive consideration that acclimation occurs within a single generation, being a non-genetically transmissible trait, one can assume that the dose integration period has an upper limit equal to the lifespan L of a healthy individual in captivity (where it can remain alive without predation, disease or resource limitations). This gives the lower limit value $\eta = \frac{\ln(2)}{L}$. The field vole *Microtus agrestis* has a longevity of 4.8 years (AnAge, 2024), leading to $L = 1.75 \times 10^3 \text{ d}$ and $\eta = 3.95 \times 10^{-4} \text{ d}^{-1}$.

In the present analysis, we consider an upper estimate for the dose integration period, to obtain a lower estimate for the parameter η , thereby maximising the number of adapted organisms. The interest here is in calculating how significant could acclimation become, since it is expected to affect a small fraction of the population. It is recommended to use a more realistic integration period of the order of one year for actual assessments, given that the average lifespan for voles in the field is 0.5 to 2 years (MacDonald, 2001). This will result in lower acclimated populations than calculated here.

4. Model results and discussion

4.1. Running the model with a single contaminant

In single contaminant mode, our model has tipping points induced by the effects equation: $\emptyset = \alpha D + \beta C + \gamma DC$. Figure 5 gives the model output for different values of $a \equiv \alpha D$ given $C = 0$, without or with considering acclimation. Due to the symmetry of the effects equation, the result is identical as would be obtained for different values of βC given $D = 0$. Note that, in Fig. 5, the model stabilises to $X = K \left(1 - \frac{d}{r}\right) = 948$ individuals for $\alpha D = 0$.

Figure 5: Result of varying $a \equiv \alpha D$ (or βC) when the other pollutant is not present.

Without acclimation, the population tipping point is αD (or βC) = 6×10^{-4} , above which the model output is an unstable quasi-shallow phase followed by an exponential fall reaching extinction at progressively shorter times. With acclimation, the tipping point is delayed until αD (or βC) = 9×10^{-4} , which for $\alpha = 2.1 \times 10^{-4}$ mGy $^{-1}$ represents a dose rate of 4.4 mGy d $^{-1}$. For the intervening values, recovery occurs after an initial dip of the population.

This result depends on the value of the parameter p_1 , currently set at 2.3×10^{-2} mGy $^{-1}$. A lower value of p_1 would result in an earlier onset of the tipping point. For example, reducing p_1 by a factor of 10 would set the tipping point αD (or βC) at 1.8×10^{-3} , equivalent to 8 mGy. Reducing by a factor of 100 would bring αD to 0.012, or 58 mGy. For this reason, it is not recommended to use of the model's acclimation mechanism to make predictions in actual assessments. It is rather advised to use it to make projections, i.e. numerically exploring its potential significance, at least until the parameter uncertainty is addressed, signalling the direction for future investigations.

4.2. Application to a mixed contamination test scenario

Figure 6 shows a series of modelling simulations testing the effect of arsenate for varying radiation dose rates ranging between 0 and 10^{-1} Gy d $^{-1}$. These simulations exclude the acclimation process, to avoid confounding factors.

In the absence of chemical pollutant, for dose rates < 3 mGy d $^{-1}$, the population reaches a lower equilibrium value, tipping-over at a dose rate of 6 mGy d $^{-1}$. This is because initially, upon depletion of the repairing pool, all potentially repairable damages revert to lethality, and the population is supported only by reproduction. However, as the reproducing capacity itself

becomes decreased, it becomes insufficient to maintain the population, leading to extinction (< 1 individual) after 1000 days.

Figure 6: Effect of adding a progressively higher chemical concentrations for a range of radiation dose rates between 0 and 15 mGy d⁻¹

In the absence of radiation, the population begins to tip over at an arsenate concentration of 5 mg kg⁻¹. Population that would have remained stable at 3 mGy d⁻¹ under zero arsenate pollutant concentration is now able to tip over at 2.5 mg kg⁻¹. From 5 mg kg⁻¹, the population is no longer able to be sustained. For higher concentrations, the tipping point is reached faster, so that at 100 mg kg⁻¹, the population is extinguished in < 1 year. Hence, the presence of a chemical pollutant increases the significance of the radiation effects by lowering the tipping point that would otherwise be higher for radiation acting alone. This demonstrates the need to consider radiation in context of contaminants when comparing exposure levels with regulatory benchmarks (Kryshev et al., 2008). Such benchmarks are based on single stressor values, so it is important to use models to verify that they are sufficiently robust in mixed exposure situations.

For zero chemical concentration, the results are consistent with a previous model (Vives i Batlle et al., 2020) predicting extinction at dose rates > 10 mGy d⁻¹. For elements of different toxicity, the tipping points would be different, allowing, in principle, to produce a comparative assessment.

Arsenate concentrations above 0.007 mg kg⁻¹ led to a population becoming extinct that would have remained otherwise stable at 0.02 Gy d⁻¹, and at 0.1 mg kg⁻¹ the chemical concentration tipped into extinction a population that would have been stable in the absence of radiation.

4.3. Derivation of dose response curves

When plotting model-predicted percentage mortality as a function of radiation dose, the resulting dose-response curve (DRC), shown in Fig. 7, can be adequately fitted to the expected Logit function $y = \frac{L}{1 + e^{-k(x-c)}}$, showing that the model is suitable to be validated with DRC data.

Figure 7: Model-derived dose-response curve showing accurate fitting by the logistic function.

It is possible to link the effects equation $f(D, C)$ for a given mixture of contaminants to the shape of the DRC for the mixture, establishing the link of α , β and $\pm\gamma$ to the CA and IA equations. The model should especially be able to show that a lower effective EC_y can be obtained for the case of independent action, due to the negative quadratic term controlled by the parameter γ causing a deviation from linearity.

4.4. Simulation to calculate effects of mixtures

It is now necessary to define a new population quantity, namely a “population half-lethal dose” $PD_{50/100}$ as the radiation dose rate ($mGy\ d^{-1}$) needed to extinguish 50% of the population in 1000 days (3 generations) in the presence of all relevant population factors (reproduction, mortality, and ecosystem resource). This is qualitatively different from the $LD_{50/30}$, which refers to effects on the individual in the absence of population factors and it is for an acute dose effect over a period of 30 days. A similar definition leads us to the $PC_{50/100}$ as the 50% lethal chemical concentration for the population ($mGy\ d^{-1}$).

4.4.1. Concentration addition case: α and $\beta > 0$ and $\gamma = 0$

By setting the chemical stressor concentration to 0 in the model, with the parameter γ set to zero, it is easy to derive numerically the $PD_{50/1000}$ by optimisation as $7.36\ mGy\ d^{-1}$. A $PC_{50/1000}$ of $3.98\ mg\ kg^{-1}$ is similarly derived by setting the radiation dose to 0. Then, $\alpha PC_{50/1000} = \beta PD_{50/1000}$ which is interpreted as the model being symmetrical in terms of radiation and chemical stressors when the results are expressed in these “toxicity equivalent” units (Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Symmetry of chemical and radiation stressors when these agents are expressed in units of αD and βC , respectively.

Next, the two stressors are considered simultaneously, multiplying $PD_{50/100}$ by α and $PC_{50/1000}$ by β so that both quantities can be compared. The value of $\alpha D + \beta C$ that generates a 50% lethality can be obtained by downscaling D and C by 50% whilst maintaining the relative proportion of both components. This situation reflects the concentration addition toxicity model. The radiation dose rate and the concentration of the chemical (arsenate in this example) simply act as dilutions of each other and can be “exchanged” into the same “currency” when multiplied by the parameters α and β , respectively, to convert them into the same radiotoxic units.

4.4.2. Antagonism and synergism: α and $\beta > 0$ and $\pm \gamma > 0$

Our model considers γ a *a priori* free parameter, but it is possible to infer it as function of α and β , as follows. The equations for X , Y , F and R in Figure 3 include a term of the type $(\alpha D + \beta C + \gamma DC)X$. As previously stated, this term is an approximative function. It can be theoretically hypothesised as the polynomial expansion of a two-parameter exponential term $(e^{\alpha D + \beta C} - 1)X$ for low values of dose or concentration. Expanding this hypothetical exponential function to the second order and neglecting α^2 and β^2 (given that these terms are

of the order of 10^{-4}), would give the approximation $e^{(\alpha D + \beta C)X} - 1 \approx \alpha D + \beta C + \alpha\beta DC$, resulting in $\gamma = \alpha\beta = 2.31 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kg mg}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$. A sensitivity analysis of γ centred around this value was performed, between the extreme values $\pm 10^{-5}$, to see the effect it would have on mixture of 50% of 7.36 mGy d^{-1} of radiation and 50% of 3.98 mg kg^{-1} of contaminant, adding to an overall halving concentration when the interactions between the two contaminants are not considered (i.e. when $\gamma = 0$). The results are shown in Figure 9. The total alive individuals at $T = 1000 \text{ d}$ follow an exponential trend $N_T = 500.12e^{-40937\gamma}$ as a function of the parameter γ ($R^2 = 0.996$). This trend is quasi-linear.

Figure 9: Sensitivity analysis of the parameter $\pm \gamma$ for the case α and $\beta > 0$, showing antagonistic and synergistic behaviour.

Positive values of γ lead to a detriment in the population compared with the case $\gamma = 0$. This implies that as γ increases, the $\text{LCD}_{50/1000}$ of the mixture decreases, which is an antagonistic (less than additive) effect. Conversely, for negative values of γ , there is an increment of the population, compared with the case $\gamma = 0$. This is a synergistic (more than additive) effect. The population increases if γ is sufficiently large, but this is clearly a non-physical result, imposing a lower value of -1×10^{-4} for γ .

4.5. Effect of acclimation

4.5.1. Effect of acclimation under constant radiation dose or chemical concentration

Figure 10 shows the effect of acclimation at different dose rates constant over a 1000-day period, for zero chemical concentration. It can be seen that (a) between 1 and 10 mGy d^{-1} , the number of acclimated organisms increases from 1% to 20% of the total population; (b) acclimated population begins to peak and subsequently decay starting from 10 mGy d^{-1} peak occurs, and the onset of this peak occurs progressively earlier as the dose increases, i.e. 800, 250 and 200 days at 10, 100 and 1000 mGy d^{-1} .

Figure 10: Effect of applying a different dose rate on the survivability of the population, both without (left) and with (right) acclimation.

The exercise was repeated for chemical concentration instead of radiation dose. Using the equivalence $\alpha D \equiv \beta C$, the concentration equivalents of the dose range 1- 1000 mGy d⁻¹ are 0.52 – 520 mg kg⁻¹. For obvious reasons, population calculations for this concentration range in absence of dose give the same results as the dose-dependent curves of Fig. 10 (left). However, acclimation behaves differently, because the probability of no-acclimation does not depend on integrated dose rate over a period, but on the concentration, as per the equation $p_c(c) = \frac{q_0 + q_1 c}{1 + q_0 + q_1 c}$. Figure 11 gives the four equivalent model simulations with acclimation enabled for these four concentrations and zero radiation dose. Due to the cumulative build-up in absorbed dose (the integral of a constant dose is monotonically increasing with time), versus a constant concentration for the chemical pollutant, more acclimated individuals are produced for radiation than with the chemical.

Figure 11: Effect of applying a different chemical concentration on the survivability of the population, with acclimation enabled.

In these simulations, acclimation is not strong enough to maintain an otherwise crashing population for the ranges of radiation dose rate or chemical concentration considered. However, for a radiation dose of 1000 mGy d⁻¹, acclimated organisms returning to healthy condition form a secondary peak of healthy individuals that succeeds in prolonging the existence of the population.

To see acclimation at work in terms of fully restoring a severely compromised population, it is necessary for the radiation dose to decrease significantly at around the time that the peak of acclimated population begins to occur.

4.5.2. Effect of acclimation in a semi-realistic accident scenario

A more realistic situation than assuming a constant radiation exposure is an accident scenario with an initial radiation peak following exponential decay. It is known that the absorbed dose rate to small mammals in the Chernobyl Red Forest decreased from 6 Gy h⁻¹ in 1986 to 150 μGy h⁻¹ in 2005 (Gaschak et al., 2011), and that by 2018, dose rates were around 48 μGy h⁻¹ for vole species (Beresford et al., 2019). A double exponential representation of the dose profile in Gy d⁻¹ combining fast decaying ¹³⁴Cs and slower-decaying ¹³⁷Cs (the two radionuclides driving the dose in this scenario) been deduced: $d_r(t) = 144e^{-\frac{1.1t}{365}} + 7.2 \times 10^{-3}e^{-\frac{0.05t}{365}}$ Gy d⁻¹, where t is the time in days (Vives i Batlle et al., 2020).

For the present illustrative study, the scenario was modified by reducing exposures by a factor of 10⁻⁴, since in a previous study (Vives i Batlle et al., 2020), vole migration from less to more contaminated zones was the main force responsible for restoring population and this is not included in the present demonstration, which would result in a collapse of the population at such dose levels. The present scenario is less acute and more suitable to illustrate the effect of acclimation. This scenario can be termed semi-realistic because the shape of the dose profile is a just a scaled-down version of reality.

The effect of acclimatising to certain (constant) values of dose is considered in Fig. 12. In this simulation, the model execution time was increased from 10³ to 10⁴ days, because it is necessary to consider the time required for acclimation to act upon the tipping point for the population.

Figure 12: Simulation of the effect of acclimation in a radiological accident scenario involving an initial peak release of ¹³⁴Cs and ¹³⁷Cs.

The model gives significantly different results when acclimation is assumed. In the scenario considered, the parameter η is assumed to be as low as permitted by the organism lifespan, to ascertain how compensating of radiation this mechanism can be in the population. The model predicts a maximum η of 0.0006 above which it is not possible to recover the vole population by acclimation. Were η to have higher value, the protected status of a limited number (< 30%) of the population would not suffice to rebuild the population.

This limitation depends both on model parameterisation and on the type of scenario (physical factors). In our example, the initial phase is dominated by the decay of ^{134}Cs . For sufficiently high values of η , not enough acclimated population forms to be able to restore the whole population. If the initial component were dominated by a faster decaying component (e.g. ^{131}I), this recovery could be more effective, highlighting that the release scenarios where acclimation is more efficient are those for which the decay half-life is significantly shorter than $1/\eta$.

In Fig. 12, the peak in acclimation occurs only when the dose rate has decreased sufficiently, just in time to temporarily sustain the population while it tries to recover. Later, the number of acclimated individuals decreases with the dwindling supply of sick individuals at low doses. The fact that this peak appears late in the simulation is a mathematical consequence of the way the acclimation probability relates to cumulative dose, not a sign that individuals are genetically adapting over long time periods.

With this type of model, it should be possible in future to compare specific contamination modelling scenarios with benchmark values such as the ICRP DCRLs for non-human biota (ICRP, 2008), ascertaining whether acclimation can be important enough to increase the lower level of the dose bands in these scenarios.

4.6. Sensitivity analysis

Additional sensitivity analysis was performed on the acclimation mechanism, which remains the more conjectural part of the model. Fig. 13 gives an analysis of the acclimated population for different dose rates at zero concentration, and different concentrations at zero dose, to highlight the behaviour of the model when varying the amount of radiation or arsenate.

Figure 13: Sensitivity analysis of the acclimated population as a function of dose rate (left) and concentration (right)

For dose rates $\leq 7 \text{ mGy d}^{-1}$ or concentrations $\leq 3.1 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, a progressively larger acclimated population is reached, arriving at equilibrium sooner as the radiation dose or concentration increases. A tipping point occurs at a dose rate of 8 mGy d^{-1} or a pollutant concentration of 3.6 mg kg^{-1} , whereupon acclimated population forms a quasi-symmetric peak whose maximum sets on earlier and reduces in level at progressive higher levels. This is in keeping with the fact that, as the integrated dose increases, the probability of non-acclimation p_R decreases, but it starts to

increase again after a certain threshold in accord with the equations $p_R = \frac{p_0 + p_1 \int_{T-L}^T DR(t) dt}{1 + p_0 + p_1 \int_{T-L}^T DR(t) dt}$ and $p_C = \frac{q_0 + q_1 C}{1 + q_0 + q_1 C}$ which tends to 1 as the integral $\int_{T-L}^T DR(t) dt$ (for radiation) or the concentration C (for the chemical) tends to infinite. If both chemicals are present, then the equation $p = p_R(DR) + p_C(c) - p_R(DR)p_C(c)$ would apply, intensifying the above behaviour.

A variational analysis of the parameter η was performed for dose rates before and after the tipping point observed Fig. 13; namely, 1 and 10 mGy d⁻¹. This analysis was also carried out for the concentration equivalents to dose of 0.52 mg kg⁻¹ and 5.2 mg kg⁻¹, obtained by multiplying by the ratio $\frac{\alpha}{\beta} = 0.5238 \text{ mg mGy}^{-1} \text{ d kg}^{-1}$. The results are given in Fig. 14.

Figure 14: Sensitivity analysis of the parameter η for a dose rate of 1 mGy d⁻¹ below the tipping point of Fig. 14 (left) and 10 mGy d⁻¹, above tipping point (right)

For the case of radiation, the change in model output is lower for the higher dose of 10 mGy d⁻¹, in the sense that an acclimated population peak remains, with its centroid shifting relatively little (from 850 to 750 days as η increases) whilst the maximum of the acclimated population

diminishes by a factor of 2 for a one-order-of-magnitude increase in η . For the lower dose rate of 1 mGy d⁻¹, a wider range of behaviours is observed from unrestricted growth for low values of η to a peaking and subsequent reduction of the acclimated population for $\eta \geq 0.0005$. In all cases, increasing η by a factor of 110 reduces acclimation by an order of magnitude.

For the chemical case, the maximum number of acclimated individuals is inferior for both concentrations than for doses, in keeping with the fact that for radiation, the primary magnitude (dose rate) is integrated, so for a constant activity concentration, the integrated dose increases with time. For the lower concentration, the population does not peak for $\eta \geq 0.0005$. lastly, for the highest concentration, the peak of the population is somewhat displaced from 750 – 850 days down to 725 – 750 days.

The variability of the acclimation probability parameters p_0 and p_1 was also assessed. For low doses, $\int_{T-L}^T DR(t) dt$ is small and $p_R \approx \frac{1}{1+p_0}$. At high doses, the expression tends to 0, and so does the acclimated population. Fig. 15 shows the result of varying p_0 and p_1 within one order of magnitude below and above the stated values of Table 1, for 1 and 10 mGy d⁻¹.

Figure 15: Effect of varying p_0 on the acclimated population at dose rates of 1 mGy d⁻¹ (left) and 10 mGy d⁻¹ (right).

The results show that the model is not strongly sensitive to p_0 , given the twofold variation when p_0 changes from 0 to 1. The parameter p_1 is more sensitive. At 1 mGy d⁻¹, an order of magnitude increase in p_1 induces a population reduction by a factor of 42. At 10 mGy d⁻¹, variation is by a factor of 28.

Due to the large value of q_1 (74.4 kg mg⁻¹), the model is virtually insensitive to a ± 1 -order of magnitude of the parameter q_0 at both 0.52 and 5.2 mg kg⁻¹. The parameter q_1 shows a similar pattern of variation as p_1 (Fig. 16), except that the maximum number of acclimated individuals is lower in comparison with the analysis for dose rate. Moreover, for the lower concentration, the population does not peak for any of the q_1 values considered.

Figure 16: Effect of varying q_1 on the acclimated population at concentrations of 0.52 mg kg⁻¹ (left) and 5.2 mg kg⁻¹ (right).

5. Conclusions and perspectives for future work

The model presented here provides a conceptual framework to assess the effect of a radiation/chemical mixture at the population level. The model can be used to inform ongoing regulatory debates on the robustness of protection benchmarks for wildlife risk assessment in mixed exposure situations.

The next step for this research is to apply the model to a realistic scenario. A trial assessment using this model is currently underway under the IAEA MEREIA Project's Working group 5 on Multiple Stressors in a Fjord. From a regulation perspective, consistency of approach between environmental impact assessment in ecotoxicology and in radiation protection at a regulatory level is a goal. Therefore, NORM sites and legacies could be a good first practical application of the model in this regard.

The approach presented here can help formulate regulatory questions about the effects of mixed stressors on populations, such as what are the most restrictive mixed exposure situations. The parameters α , β and γ can be used as index quantities to classify polluted sites in impact assessments. More generally, our study provides the basis for opening a dialogue between

radioecologists, ecotoxicologists, and regulators to assess the environmental effects of radioactive and chemical hazards consistently.

The model functions primarily as a CA approach. From the literature review, it should therefore be applicable to a significant number of cases, with the added possibility to represent antagonism and synergism: If a dose-response curve is available for the contaminants, one can deduce the parameters α , β and from the shape of the DRC, and assess how different from zero γ is. Further parameterisation changes can be made to accommodate IA behaviour by imposing independent fecundity and repair rates ($\alpha_f \neq \beta_f$ and $\alpha_r \neq \beta_r$, respectively). In terms of practical application, the limitation here is more on the side of the experimental data available to ascertain the mode of action of the contaminants, rather than on the model itself.

Future avenues of model development could involve (a) exploring nonlinearities in model solutions, (b) exploring new forms of $f(D,C)$ to model additive, synergistic or antagonistic effects with link to CA and IA assumptions and (c) introducing TK elements into the present model to predict the transfer of substances from the external environment to the biota, leading to a full TK – TD model (already in progress).

There is potential for integrating the approach with the adverse outcome pathway (AOP) methodology for radiation-induced effects in wildlife (Tollefsen et al., 2022). This could be achieved by replacing the single-compartment repairing pool with a submodel containing a chain of compartments based on the structured chain of biological events leading to damages. The compartments would represent the series of key events between initiating events and the adverse outcomes. Kinetic rates or probabilities would be introduced to represent the chain's dynamics.

An important recommendation for future work is to find possible empirical validation routes for the model with laboratory studies (e.g. *Drosophila* experiments, in vitro single cell cultures and *Lemna minor* laboratory experiments). There are no field studies of the long-term effects of mixed contaminants and radiation for wildlife populations in the environment. Full model validation can be attempted when these become available. The potential for using this model for experiment or field study design should not be overlooked. Benchmarking with other modelling approaches (e.g. DebTox modelling or the msPAF approach) are also foreseen, signalling the route for future investigations.

To turn this paper's conceptual model into a practical tool, it should be made user friendly and work with "indicators" to show when the model points towards population effects that must be considered because it puts the compliance with the selected benchmark into question. Also, the model should point out clearly to the user what the sources of uncertainty are and what degree of conservatism is applied to the parameters. For example, a "traffic light" system could be devised, with indication of where the mixed exposure situation causes population tipping points in relation to the protection benchmarks, and highlighting the reliability of the assessment based on quantified uncertainties.

6. Acknowledgements

This research was carried out within the RadoNorm project and received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2019-2020 under grant agreement No 900009.

The author wishes thanks Dr Geert Biermans (SCK CEN) for his advice and comments on the regulatory aspects of this study.

REFERENCES

- Accolla, C., Vaugeois, M., Grimm, V., Moore, A.P., Rueda-Cediel, P., Schmolke, A., Forbes, V.E., 2020. A review of key features and their implementation in unstructured, structured, and agent-based population models for ecological risk assessment. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management* 17, 521-540.
- Alonzo, F., Hertel-Aas, T., Real, A., Lance, E., Garcia-Sanchez, L., Bradshaw, C., Vives i Batlle, J., Garnier-Laplace, J., 2016. Population modeling to compare chronic external gamma radiotoxicity between individual and population endpoints in four taxonomic groups. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 152, 46-59.
- Alonzo, F., Horemans, N., Oughton, D., Adam-Guillermin, C., Lecomte-Pradines, C., Parisot, F., Buisset-Goussen, A., Zimmer, E., Real, A., Garnier-Laplace, J., 2015. STAR Deliverable (D-N°5.5). Protection criteria: Integrating radiation protection from molecules to populations and evaluation of group specific criteria. European Commission, 7th Framework, Contract N(Fission-2010-3.5.1-269672), 69 pp.
- Alonzo, F., Vives i Batlle, J., Hertel-Aas, T., Bradshaw, C., Vandenhove, H., Garnier-Laplace, J., 2012. Life history traits, radiosensitivity and population modeling: methods to extrapolate from individual endpoints to population dynamics. STAR Deliverable D-N°5.2, Seventh Euratom Framework Programme for Nuclear Research & Training Activities Contract Fission-2010-3.5.1-269672, 31/07/2012, 125 pp.
- Alonzo, F., Zimmer, E., Plaire, D., Buisset-Goussen, A., Adam-Guillermin, C., Lecomte-Pradines, C., Horemans, N., Hinton, T., 2014. STAR Deliverable (D-N°5.4). Understanding the “metabolic” mode of actions of two different types of radiation using biokinetics/DEBtox models. European Commission, 7th Framework, Contract N(Fission-2010-3.5.1-269672), 69 pp.
- Altenburger, R., Backhaus, T., Boedeker, W., Faust, M., Scholze, M., Grimme, L.H., 2000. Predictability of the toxicity of multiple chemical mixtures to *Vibrio fischeri*: Mixtures composed of similarly acting chemicals. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 19, 2341–2347.
- AMP, 2020. AddMyPet: Online database of DEB parameters, implied properties and referenced underlying data.
- AnAge, 2024. The Animal Ageing and Longevity Database. A database of ageing and life history in animals, including extensive longevity records. Available online: <http://genomics.senescence.info/species> (accessed 1 May 2024).
- Ashauer, R., Boxall, A., Brown, C.D., 2007. New ecotoxicological model to simulate survival of aquatic invertebrates after exposure to fluctuating and sequential pulses of pesticides. *Environmental Science & Technology* 41, 1480-1486.
- Augustine, S., Gagnaire, B., Adam-Guillermin, C., Kooijman, S., 2012. Effects of uranium on the metabolism of zebrafish, *Danio rerio*. *Aquatic Toxicology* 119, 9-26.
- Baas, J., Stefanowicz, A.M., Klimek, B., Laskowski, R., Kooijman, S.A.L.M., 2010a. Model-based experimental design for assessing effects of mixtures of chemicals. *Environmental Pollution* 158, 115-120.
- Baas, J., T., Jager, S.A.L.M., Kooijman, B., 2010b. A review of DEB theory in assessing toxic effects of mixtures. *Science of the Total Environment* 408, 3740–3745.
- Backhaus, T., Altenburger, R., Boedeker, W., Faust, M., Scholze, M., Grimme, L.H., 2000. Predictability of the toxicity of multiple mixtures of dissimilarly acting chemicals to *Vibrio Fischeri*. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 19, 2348–2356.
- Beaugelin-Seiller, K., Della-Vedova, C., Garnier-Laplace, J., 2020. Transforming acute ecotoxicity data into chronic data: a statistical method to better inform radiological risk for non-human species. *Environmental Science & Technology* 54, 12376–12382.

- Beaumelle, L., Della Vedova, C., Beaugelin-Seiller, K., Garnier-Laplace, J., Gilbin, R., 2017. Ecological risk assessment of mixtures of radiological and chemical stressors: Methodology to implement an msPAF approach. *Environmental Pollution* 231, 1421-1432.
- Beresford, N.A., Barnett, C.L., Gashchak, S., Maksimenko, A., Guliaichenko, E., Wood, M.D., Izquierdo, M., 2019. Radionuclide transfer to wildlife at a 'Reference Site' in the Chernobyl Exclusion Zone and resultant radiation exposures. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 211, 1-12.
- Beresford, N.A., Vives i Batlle, J., 2021. Radiological environmental protection of wildlife: modelling the exposure and effects. Joint Summary Report of Working Groups 8 and 9 (MODARIA I) and Working Group 5 (MODARIA II) - Modelling and Data for Radiological Impact Assessments (MODARIA) Programme. IAEA TECDOC No. 1986, International Atomic Energy Agency, 86 pp.
- Bodnar, I.S., Cheban, E.V., 2022. Combined action of gamma radiation and exposure to copper ions on *Lemna minor* L. *International Journal of Radiation Biology* 98, 1120-1129.
- Bodnar, I.S., Cheban, E.V., 2023. Joint effects of gamma radiation and zinc on duckweed *Lemna minor* L. *Aquatic Toxicology* 257, 106438.
- Borgmann, U., Norwood, W.P., Dixon, D.G., 2008. Modelling bioaccumulation and toxicity of metal mixtures. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment* 14, 266-289.
- Bradshaw, C., Meseh, D.A., Alasawi, H., Quiang, M., Snoeijis-Leijonmalm, P., Nascimento, F.J.A., 2019. Joint effects of gamma radiation and cadmium on subcellular-, individual- and population-level endpoints of the green microalga *Raphidocelis subcapitata*. *Aquatic Toxicology* 211, 217-226.
- Caswell, N., 2001. *Matrix Population Models: Construction, Analysis, and Interpretation*. Sinauer Associates, 772 pp.
- Cedergreen, N., Christensen, A.M., Kamper, A., Kudsk, P., Mathiassen, S.K., Streibig, J.C., Sørensen, H., 2008. A review of independent action compared to concentration addition as reference models for mixtures of compounds with different molecular target sites. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 27, 1621-1632.
- Cedergreen, N., Dalhoff, K., Li, D., Gottardi, M., Kretschmann, A.C., 2017. Can toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic modeling be used to understand and predict synergistic interactions between chemicals? *Environmental Science & Technology* 51, 14379-14389.
- Chen, W.-Q., Wang, W.-X., Tan, Q.-G., 2017. Revealing the complex effects of salinity on copper toxicity in an estuarine clam *Potamocorbula laevis* with a toxicokinetic-toxicodynamic model. *Environmental Pollution* 222, 323-330.
- Citra, M.J., 1997. Modelmaker 3.0 for Windows. *Journal of Chemical Information and Computer Sciences* 37, 1198-1200.
- Copplestone, D., Hingston, J.L., Real, A., 2008. The development and purpose of the FREDERICA radiation effects database. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 99, 1456-1463.
- De Schamphelaere, K.A.C., Heijerick, D.G., Janssen, C.R., 2002. Refinement and field validation of a biotic ligand model predicting acute copper toxicity to *Daphnia magna*. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part C: Toxicology & Pharmacology* 133, 243-258.
- de Zwart, D., Posthuma, L., 2009. Complex mixture toxicity for single and multiple species: proposed methodologies. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 24, 2665-2676.
- Escher, B., Braun, G., Zarfl, C., 2020. Exploring the concepts of concentration addition and independent action using a linear low-effect mixture model. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 39, 2552-2559.
- Focks, A., Luttk, R., Zorn, M., Brock, T., Roex, E., Van der Linden, T., Van den Brink, P.J., 2014. A simulation study on effects of exposure to a combination of pesticides used in an orchard and tuber crop

on the recovery time of a vulnerable aquatic invertebrate. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 33, 1489-1498.

FREDERICA, 2006. FREDERICA Radiation Effects Database. Available from: <http://www.frederica-online.org/mainpage.asp>.

Galic, N., Hommen, U., Baveco, J.M.H., Van den Brink, P.J., 2010. Potential application of population models in the European ecological risk assessment of chemicals II: Review of models and their potential to address environmental protection aims. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management* 6, 338-360.

Gao, Y., Feng, J., Han, F., Zhu, L., 2016. Application of biotic ligand and toxicokinetic-toxicodynamic modeling to predict the accumulation and toxicity of metal mixtures to zebrafish larvae. *Environmental Pollution* 213, 16-29.

Garnier-Laplace, J., Beaugelin-Seiller, K., Gilbin, R., Della-Vedova, C., Jolliet, O., Payet, J., 2009. A Screening Level Ecological Risk Assessment and ranking method for liquid radioactive and chemical mixtures released by nuclear facilities under normal operating conditions. *Radioprotection* 44, 903-908.

Gaschak, S.P., Maklyuk, Y.A., Maksimenko, A.M., Bondarkov, M.D., Jannik, G.T., Farfán, E.B., 2011. Radiation ecology issues associated with murine rodents and shrews in the Chernobyl exclusion zone. *Health Physics* 101, 416-430.

Gonzales, A.K., Donaher, S.E., Wattier, B.D., Martinez, N.E., 2023. Exposure of *Lemna minor* (common duckweed) to mixtures of uranium and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA). *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 42, 2412-2421.

Goussen, B., Pery, A.R.R., Bonzom, J.-M., Beaudouin, R., 2015. Transgenerational adaptation to pollution changes energy allocation in populations of nematodes. *Environmental Science and Technology* 49, 12500-12508.

Hansul, S., Fettweis, A., Smolders, E., De Schamphelaere, K., 2021. Interactive metal mixture toxicity to *Daphnia magna* populations as an emergent property in a dynamic energy budget Individual-Based Model. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 40, 3034-3048.

Hartwig, A., 2016. Arsenic and its inorganic compounds (with the Exception of Arsine). The MAK-Collection for Occupational Health and Safety, Part I: MAK Commission Value Documentations, Vol. 21. DFG, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co., KGaA, Weinheim.

Heier, L.S., Teien, H.C., Oughton, D., Tollefsen, K.E., Olsvik, P.A., Rosseland, B.O., Lind, O.C., Farmen, E., Skipperud, L., Salbu, B., 2013. Sublethal effects in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) exposed to mixtures of copper, aluminium and gamma radiation. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 121, 33-42.

Heijerick, D.G., De Schamphelaere, K.A.C., Janssen, C.R., 2009. Predicting acute zinc toxicity for *Daphnia magna* as a function of key water chemistry characteristics: Development and validation of a biotic ligand model. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 21, 1309-1315.

ICRP, 2008. Environmental Protection: The Concept and use for Reference Animals and Plants. International Commission on Radiological Protection Publication 108, Annals of the ICRP 38(4-6), Elsevier Ltd., 76 pp.

ICRP, 2009. Transfer Parameters for Reference Animals and Plants. International Commission on Radiological Protection. Environmental Protection Publication 114. Annals of the ICRP 39(6), Elsevier, Oxford.

Jager, T., Gudmundsdóttir, E.M., Cedergreen, N., 2014. Dynamic Modeling of Sublethal Mixture Toxicity in the Nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Environmental Science and Technology* 48, 7026-7033.

Jager, T., Zimmer, E.I., 2012. Simplified Dynamic Energy Budget model for analysing ecotoxicity data. *Ecological Modelling* 225, 74-81.

- Jonker, M., Svendsen, C., Bedaux, J.J.M., Bongers, M., Kammenga, J.E., 2005. Significance testing of synergistic/antagonistic, dose level-dependent, or dose ratio-dependent effects in mixture dose-response analysis *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 24, 2701-2713.
- Koch, J., De Schampelaere, K.A.C., 2000. Estimating inter-individual variability of dynamic energy budget model parameters for the copepod *Nitocra spinipes* from existing life-history data. *Ecological Modelling* 431, 109091.
- Kooijman, S., 1986. Energy Budgets Can Explain Body Size Relations. *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 121, 269-282.
- Kooijman, S.A.L.M., 2000. *Dynamic Energy and Mass Budgets in Biological Systems (Second Edition)*. Cambridge University Press, 424 pp.
- Kooijman, S.A.L.M., Bedaux, J.J.M., 1996. Analysis of toxicity tests on *Daphnia* survival and reproduction. *Water Research* 30, 1711-1723.
- Kryshev, A.I., Ryabov, I.N., 2000. A dynamic model of ^{137}Cs accumulation by fish of different age classes. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 50, 221-233.
- Kryshev, A.I., Sazykina, T.G., 2015. Modelling the effects of ionizing radiation on survival of animal population: acute versus chronic exposure. *Radiation and Environmental Biophysics* 54, 103-109.
- Kryshev, A.I., Sazykina, T.G., Badalian, K.D., 2006. Mathematical simulation of dose-effect relationships for fish eggs exposed chronically to ionizing radiation. *Radiation and Environmental Biophysics* 45, 195-201.
- Kryshev, A.I., Sazykina, T.G., Sanina, K.D., 2008. Modelling of effects due to chronic exposure of a fish population to ionizing radiation. *Radiation and Environmental Biophysics* 47, 121-129.
- Lance, E., Alonzo, F., Garcia-Sanchez, L., Beaugelin-Seiller, K., Garnier-Laplace, J., 2012. Modeling population-level consequences of chronic external gamma irradiation in aquatic invertebrates under laboratory conditions. *Science of the Total Environment* 429, 206-214.
- Lecomte-Pradines, C., Hertel-Aas, T., Cutris, C., Gilbin, R., Oughton, D., Alonzo, F., 2017. A dynamic energy-based model to analyze sublethal effects of chronic gamma irradiation in the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health - Part A* 80, 830-844.
- Loewe, S., Muischnek, H., 1926. Über Kombinationswirkungen. *Naunyn-Schmiedebergs Archiv für Experimentelle Pathologie und Pharmakologie* 114, 313-326.
- MacDonald, D., 2001. *The Encyclopedia of Mammals*. Andromeda Oxford Limited.
- Mackay, D., McCarty, L.S., Arnot, J.A., 2014. Relationships between exposure and dose in aquatic toxicity tests for organic chemicals. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 33, 9.
- Margerit, A., Gómez, E., Gilbin, R., 2016. Dynamic energy-based modeling of uranium and cadmium joint toxicity to *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Chemosphere* 146, 405-412.
- Margerit, A., Lecomte, P.C., Svendsen, C., Frelon, S., Gomez, E., Gilbin, R., 2015. Nested interactions in the combined toxicity of uranium and cadmium to the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 118, 139-148.
- Massarin, S., Alonzo, F., Garcia-Sanchez, L., Gilbin, R., Garnier-Laplace, J., Poggiale, J.-C., 2010. Effects of chronic uranium exposure on life history and physiology of *Daphnia magna* over three successive generations. *Aquatic Toxicology* 99, 309-319.
- Massarin, S., Beaudouin, R., Zeman, F., Floriani, M., R., G., Alonzo, F., Pery, A.R.R., 2011. Biology-based modeling to analyze uranium toxicity data on *Daphnia magna* in a multigeneration study. *Environmental Science and Technology* 45, 4151-4158.
- Matyja, K., 2023. Sublethal effects of binary mixtures of Cu^{2+} and Cd^{2+} on *Daphnia magna*: Standard Dynamic Energy Budget (DEB) model analysis. *Environmental Pollution* 334, 122142.

- Mebane, C.A., Chowdhury, M.J., De Schamphelaere, K., Lofts, S., Paquin, P.R., Santore, R.C., Wood, C.M., 2020. Metal bioavailability models: current status, lessons learned, considerations for regulatory use, and the path forward. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 39, 60-84.
- Metz, J.A.J., Diekmann, O., 1986. *The Dynamics of Physiologically Structured Populations*, vol. 68. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
- Mintram, K.S., Maynard, S.K., Brown, A.R., Boyd, R., Johnston, A.S.A., Sibly, R.M., Thorbeke, P., Tyler, C.R., 2020. Applying a mechanistic model to predict interacting effects of chemical exposure and food availability on fish populations. *Aquatic Toxicology* 224, 105483.
- Mothersill, C., Smith, R.W., Heier, L.S., Teien, H.C., Lind, O.C., Seymour, C., Oughton, D., Salbu, B., 2014. Radiation-induced bystander effects in the Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.) following mixed exposure to copper and aluminum combined with low-dose gamma radiation. *Radiation and Environmental Biophysics* 53, 103-114.
- Müller, J., Ruppert, H., Muramatsu, Y., Schneider, J., 2000. Reservoir sediments – a witness of mining and industrial development (malter Reservoir, eastern Erzgebirge, Germany). *Environmental Geology* 39, 1341-1351.
- Nascimento, F.J.A., Svendsen, C., Bradshaw, C., 2015. Combined Effects from γ Radiation and Fluoranthene Exposure on Carbon Transfer from Phytoplankton to Zooplankton. *Environmental Science & Technology* 49, 10624–10631.
- Nascimento, F.J.A., Svendsen, C., Bradshaw, C., 2016. Joint toxicity of cadmium and ionizing radiation on zooplankton carbon Incorporation, growth and mobility. *Environmental Science & Technology* 50, 1527–1535.
- Nisbet, R.M., Muller, E.B., Lika, K., Kooijman, S.A.L.M., 2000. From molecules to ecosystems through dynamic energy budget models. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 69, 913–926.
- Nys, C., Vlaeminck, K., Van Sprang, P., De Schamphelaere, K., 2020. A generalized bioavailability model (gBAM) for predicting chronic copper toxicity to freshwater fish. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.4806>.
- Phillips, K.G., Jacques, S.L., McCarty, O.J.T., 2012. Measurement of single cell refractive Index, dry mass, volume, and density using a transillumination microscope. *Physical Review Letters* 109, 118105.
- Pirotta, E., Thomas, L., Costa, D., Hall, A.J., Harris, C.M., Harwood, J., Kraus, S., Miller, P.J., Moore, M., Photopoulou, T., Rolland, R., Schwacke, L., Simmons, S., Southall, B., Tyack, P.L., 2022. Understanding the combined effects of multiple stressors: A new perspective on a longstanding challenge. *Science of the Total Environment* 821, 153322.
- Plaire, D., Bourdineaud, J.P., Alonzo, A., Camilleri, V., Garcia-Sanchez, L., Adam-Guillermin, C., Alonzo, F., 2013. Transmission of DNA damage and increasing reprotoxic effects over two generations of *Daphnia magna* exposed to uranium. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part C* 158, 231-243.
- Railsback, S.F., Grimm, V., 2019. *Agent-based and Individual-based Modeling: A Practical Introduction*. Princeton University Press, New Jersey 2nd ed.
- Raimondo, S., Schmolke, A., Pollesch, N., Accolla, C., Galic, N., Moore, A.P., Vaugeois, M., Rueda-Cediel, P., Kanarek, A., Awkerman, J., Forbes, V.E., 2021. Pop-guide: population modeling guidance, use, interpretation, and development for ecological risk assessment. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management* 17, 767-784.
- Salbu, B., Denbeigh, J., Smith, R.W., Heier, L.S., Teien, H.C., Rosseland, B.O., Oughton, D., Seymour, C.B., Mothersill, C., 2008. Environmentally relevant mixed exposures to radiation and heavy metals induce measurable stress responses in Atlantic salmon. *Environmental Science and Technology* 42, 3441-3446.

- Salbu, B., Teien, H.C., Lind, O.C., Tollefsen, K.E., 2019. Why is the multiple stressor concept of relevance to radioecology? *International Journal of Radiation Biology* 95, 1015-1024.
- Sazykina, T., 2018. Population sensitivities of animals to chronic ionizing radiation-model predictions from mice to elephant. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 182, 177-182.
- Sazykina, T., Kryshev, A., 2016. Simulation of population response to ionizing radiation in an ecosystem with a limiting resource - Model and analytical solutions. *Journal of environmental radioactivity* 151, 50-57.
- Sazykina, T.G., Kryshev, A.I., 2012. Radiation effects in generic populations inhabiting a limiting environment. *Radiation and Environmental Biophysics* 51, 215-221.
- Tan, Q.-G., Wang, W.-X., 2012. Two-Compartment Toxicokinetic–Toxicodynamic Model to Predict Metal Toxicity in *Daphnia magna*. *Environmental Science & Technology* 46, 9709–9715.
- Tayibi, H., Choura, M., López, F.A., Alguacil, F.J., López-Delgado, A., 2009. Environmental impact and management of phosphogypsum. *Journal of Environmental Management* 90, 2377-2386.
- Tollefsen, K.E., Alonzo, F., Beresford, N.A., Brede, D.A., Dufourcq-Sekatcheff, E., Gilbin, R., Horemans, N., Hurem, S., Laloi, P., Maremonti, E., Oughton, D., Simon, S., Song, Y., Wood, M.D., Xie, L., Frelon, S., 2022. Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) for radiation-induced reproductive effects in environmental species: state of science and identification of a consensus AOP network. *Int. J. Rad. Biol.* 17:1-134. *International Journal of Radiation Biology* 17, 1-34.
- Van Dyck, I., 2023. Application of *Lemna minor* in site remediation strategies.
- Vandenhove, H., Horemans, N., Gilbin, R., Lofts, S., Real, A., Bradshaw, C., Février, L., Thørring, H., Brown, J., Oughton, D., Mora, J.C., Adam-Guillermin, C., Alonzo, F., Saenen, E., Spurgeon, D., Salbu, B., 2011. Critical review of existing approaches, methods and tools for mixed contaminant exposure, effect and risk assessment in ecotoxicology and evaluation of their usefulness for radioecology. EC STAR Deliverable DN°4.1, Contract Number:Fission 2010-3.5.1-269672, 244 pp.
- Vandenhove, H., Vives i Batlle, J., Sweeck, L., 2015. Potential radiological impact of the phosphate industry on wildlife. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 141, 14-23.
- Vanhoudt, N., Vandenhove, H., Horemans, N., Wannijn, J., Van Hees, M., Vangronsveld, J., Cuypers, A., 2010. The combined effect of uranium and gamma radiation on biological responses and oxidative stress induced in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 101, 923-930.
- Vives i Batlle, J., 2012. Dual age class population model to assess radiation dose effects to non-human biota populations. *Radiation and Environmental Biophysics* 51, 225-243.
- Vives i Batlle, J., Biermans, G., Coppelstone, D., Kryshev, A., Melintescu, A., Mothersill, C., Sazykina, T., Seymour, C., Smith, K., Wood, M.D., 2022. Towards an ecological modelling approach for assessing ionising radiation impact on wildlife populations. *Journal of Radiological Protection* 42, 020507.
- Vives i Batlle, J., Sazykina, T., Kryshev, A., Monte, L., Kawaguchi, I., 2012. Inter-comparison of population models for the calculation of radiation dose effects to wildlife. *Radiation and Environmental Biophysics* 51, 399-410.
- Vives i Batlle, J., Sazykina, T., Kryshev, A., Wood, M.D., Smith, K., Coppelstone, D., Biermans, G., 2020. Modelling the effects of ionising radiation on a vole population from the Chernobyl Red forest in an ecological context. *Ecological Modelling* 438, 109306.
- Vives i Batlle, J., Wilson, R.C., Watts, S.J., Jones, S.R., McDonald, P., Vives-Lynch, S., 2008. Dynamic model for the assessment of radiological exposure to marine biota. *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 99, 1711-1730.
- Vives i Batlle, J., Wilson, R.C., Watts, S.J., McDonald, P., Jones, S.R., Vives-Lynch, S.M., Craze, A., 2009. Approach to the assessment of risk from chronic radiation to populations of European lobster, *Homarus gammarus* (L.). *Radiation and Environmental Biophysics* 49, 67-85.

- Vlaeminck, K., Viaene, K.P.J., Van Sprang, P., De Schamphelaere, K.A.C., 2021. Development and validation of a mixture toxicity implementation in the Dynamic Energy Budget–Individual-Based Model: Effects of copper and zinc on *Daphnia magna* populations. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 40, 513-527.
- Vlaeminck, K., Viaene, K.P.J., Van Sprang, P., De Schamphelaere, K.A.C., 2022. Predicting combined effects of chemical Stressors: Population-level effects of organic chemical mixtures with a dynamic energy budget individual-based model. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 41, 2240-2258.
- Wang, W.-X., Tan, Q.-G., 2019. Applications of dynamic models in predicting the bioaccumulation, transport and toxicity of trace metals in aquatic organisms. *Environmental Pollution* 252.
- Whicker, F.W., Schultz, V., 1982. *Radioecology: Nuclear Energy and the environment*. Vol. 1. CRC press, Inc. Boca Raton, Florida.
- Wodarz, D., Sorace, R., Komarova, N.L., 2014. Dynamics of Cellular Responses to Radiation. *PLOS Computational Biology* 10, 1-11.
- Yang, L., Feng, J., Gao, Y., Zhu, L., 2021. Role of Toxicokinetic and Toxicodynamic Parameters in Explaining the Sensitivity of Zebrafish Larvae to Four Metals. *Environmental Science and Technology* 55, 8965–8976.